

INFLUENCE OF STRESS FIELD AT OVERLAP EDGE OF CFRP SINGLE-LAP JOINT ON FIBER OPTIC DISTRIBUTED SENSING USING EMBEDDED FBG

D. Wada^{*1}, X. Ning¹, H. Murayama¹

¹ School of Engineering, The University of Tokyo, Tokyo, Japan

* Corresponding author (daichi_wd@giso.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp)

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1 Introduction

Adhesive bonding is one of the applicable joint for assembling composites. It causes less stress concentrations compared with mechanically fastened joints, reduces weight and has better fatigue properties [1].

Stress or strain fields at joint interfaces are informative for the purpose of assessing the quality of joint manufacturing, detecting damage and evaluating residual strength. In this regards, theoretical approaches [2-5] as well as numerical approaches with finite element analysis (FEA) [6-8] have been proposed in order to determine them. However, direct measurements of strain fields at the joint interface had been challenge.

Recently optical fiber sensors demonstrate promising capability for direct measurements of strain fields at the joint interface because they can be embedded into substrates and adhesives [9]. Fiber Bragg gratings (FBGs) are one of the candidates for such embedded sensors with high sensitivity.

One of the difficulties of strain measurements using FBGs is that the Bragg spectrum is disturbed and becomes unable to be interpreted when non-uniform longitudinal strain and/or transverse stress are applied within the length of the FBGs [10]. Individual profiles of spectra at individual reflection locations are superimposed onto the single spectra observed by a photo-detector.

We have developed fiber optic distributed measurement system based on optical frequency domain reflectometry (OFDR) in order to demodulate Bragg spectra when non-uniform strain and stress distributions are applied to FBGs [11, 12]. Using signal processing based on short time Fourier transform, the OFDR system has demonstrated (D1). This signal, D_1 , is used as a sampling trigger for the signal in Interferometer 2. D_1 is expressed as

$$D_1 = 2 \left\{ 1 + \cos(2n_{eff} L_R k) \right\}, \quad (1)$$

capability of strain distribution monitoring at the joint interface [13].

The OFDR system shows a spatial resolution of less than 1 mm, which has been expected to be sufficient to monitor approximate profile of strain distributions. However, its applicability needs to be examined especially at regions of stress/strain concentrations, which often cause severe disturbance of Bragg spectra.

In this paper, we embedded an FBG to a carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) single-lap bonded joint and demonstrated monitoring at the joint interface. We especially focused on the overlap edge of the bonded joint where stress/strain concentrations occur. We investigated their influence on the distributed monitoring results.

2 OFDR measurement system

Our OFDR system is depicted in Fig. 1. The typical sensing system consists of a tunable laser source, a PC with an A/D converter and two interferometers. In this paper we used a long-length FBG with the length of 10 cm.

The concept of the sensing principle can be introduced based on an approximated description which is seen in the work of Childers *et al* [14]. The approximation is valid when FBGs with low-reflectivity are used. In our case the reflectivity of the FBG was less than 5 %.

The incident light is split at coupler 1 (C1) and proceeds into Interferometer 1 and 2. In Interferometer 1, reflected lights from mirror 1 (M1) and 2 (M2) are interfered and detected at detector 1

where n_{eff} is the effective refractive index of the optical fiber, k is the wavenumber and L_R is the path difference between M1 and M2. By triggering D_1 ,

the constant interval of the wavenumber, Δk , is obtained as

$$\Delta k = \frac{\pi}{n_{eff} L_R}. \quad (2)$$

In interferometer 2, reflected lights from the FBG and M3 are interfered and detected at D2. This signal, D_2 , is expressed as

$$D_2 = \sum_i R_i(k) \cos(2n_{eff} L_i k), \quad (3)$$

where R_i is the reflected spectrum in the i th section of the FBG and L_i is the path difference between i th section and M3. D_2 contains the information of Bragg spectrum in the term of R_i and information of the position in the frequency.

We apply signal processing based on short-time Fourier transform (STFT) to D_2 . A window function extracts a certain section of wavenumber of D_2 and Fourier transform is applied to it. As a result, the power distribution in the sense of frequency is obtained. By sliding the window function over the whole section of wavenumber, the power profile is obtained on the map of frequency vs wavenumber.. Converting frequency to position and wavenumber to wavelength, the spatial distributions of Bragg spectra are obtained eventually. Figure 2 shows an experimentally obtained example of the map, which is called spectrogram. The horizontal and vertical axes represent wavelength and position, respectively, and the color represents the power. The distribution of the Bragg spectra of a 10 cm FBG is seen at the location of 4.44 – 4.54 m. In this paper, Hanning window with the length of 400 pm was used initially, which resulted in the spatial resolution of 0.61 mm. The window slide was adjusted to achieve 5 pm resolution of wavelength.

3 Experimental and Simulation Conditions

We embedded the long-length FBG into a unidirectional CFRP substrate by co-curing as seen in Fig. 3. The CFRP substrates were made from prepregs [0₁₀] (Q-111E, Toho Tenax Co., Ltd.). Silicon rubbers were set at both ends of the prepregs in order to stop resin flow. A Teflon film was inserted between the optical fiber and the prepregs in order to keep a certain section of the optical fiber from embedded. The prepregs, optical fiber, silicon rubbers and Teflon film were set in metal molds to which heat and pressure were applied. The other

substrate was molded in the same manner without FBGs.

Two CFRP substrates, one was with the FBG and the other without FBGs, were bonded by adhesive films (Newport 102, Newport Adhesives and Composites, Inc.). This process was performed using metal molds as seen in Fig. 4. The thickness of the adhesive was controlled to be 0.2 mm. The dimensions of the manufactured bonded joint are seen in Fig. 5. Tabs were bonded at both ends of the joint using the same adhesive films in order for the tensile tests.

In loading tests, we applied tensile loads to the joint with load steps of 0, 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 kgf. The distributions of Bragg spectra were monitored by OFDR in each load step.

In order to compare the strain distributions which are calculated from the results of OFDR measurements with theoretical values, we conducted FEA. X-Y-Z coordinate for the finite element model is also shown in Fig. 5. We built 2-D finite element model of y-z plane. The meshes of the finite element model at a joint edge are seen in Fig. 6. The mesh size was controlled to be 0.05 mm in thickness-wise at the adhesive. Displacements of nodes at the joint ends were coupled, and the displacement of either end was fixed, whereas the load was applied to the other as depicted in Fig. 7. Plane strain condition was applied. We did not model the existence of the FBG in the 2-D model. Strains and stresses of the CFRP at locations where the FBG was embedded were calculated. Material properties used in FEA are listed in Table 1.

4 Simulation and Experimental Results

Figure 8 shows longitudinal strain (strain z) and principal transverse stresses (stress x and y) distributions calculated by FEA when the tensile load of 200 kgf is applied. In this case, the principal axes of transverse stress agree with x and y axes. It can be seen from the results that transverse stresses have their peak values at the both edges of the joint. This is due to the stress concentrations. On the other hand, longitudinal strain has its peak at the joint edge of $z = 25$ mm, whereas strain is zero at the free edge of the joint ($z = 0$ mm).

In the sense of birefringence, it can be said from the calculated stress distributions that both two edges of

the joints are the locations where maximum Bragg peak splits can occur. At the location of $z = 25$ mm, stress x , σ_x , was 14.2 MPa and stress y , σ_y , was 21.6 MPa. The peak split of birefringent FBGs, $\Delta\lambda$, is expressed as

$$\Delta\lambda = \frac{n_{eff}^2 \lambda_B (1 + \nu) (P_{12} - P_{11})}{2E} |\sigma_x - \sigma_y|, \quad (4)$$

where λ_B is the initial Bragg wavelength, E and ν are the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio of the optical fiber core, respectively and P_{11} and P_{12} are the photoelastic coefficients. This equation derives from a previous work [15]. When $P_{11} = 0.113$, $P_{12} = 0.252$, $E = 73.1$ GPa, $\nu = 0.16$, $\lambda_B = 1550$ nm and stresses are $(\sigma_x, \sigma_y) = (14.2$ MPa, 21.6 MPa), the peak split is 0.03 nm. Considering the bandwidth of conventional FBGs, the peak split of 0.03 nm is hardly influential for the purpose of longitudinal strain estimation.

Figure 9 shows the examples of spectra of the embedded FBG. They are obtained from locations of $z = 16.0$ and 29.0 mm. Bragg spectra with distinct single peaks are observed, which validates the strain estimation based on the Bragg wavelength shift. The amount of spectral shift is larger in the case of $z = 29.0$ mm than $z = 16.0$ mm because of the difference of applied longitudinal strain as seen in the strain distribution of the simulation results in Fig. 8.

Figure 10 compares the longitudinal strain measured by the FBG and calculated by FEA at $z = 16.0$ and 29.0 mm. At both locations, the FBG and FEA results show good agreements, which indicates the applicability of this OFDR sensing method.

5 Observed Sensing Signal at Joint Overlap Edge

FBGs typically reflect Bragg spectra with a single peak, however, experimentally obtained spectrum at $z = 24.0$ mm, which is a location where stress/strain concentration occurs, had multiple peaks as shown in Fig. 11 (a). Considering that the peak splits due to the birefringence cannot be assumed as discussed in the previous chapter, the cause of the multiple peaks is thought to be the influence of the sharply varied longitudinal strain distribution.

In order to examine the influence of the sharply varied longitudinal strain, we controlled spatial response of the OFDR system and observed the profile of obtained spectra. We applied different window widths for STFT, which result in different

spatial resolutions of the distributed sensing. We applied 400 pm, 600 pm, 800 pm and 1000 pm of the window width to STFT, which correspond to spatial resolutions of 0.61 mm, 0.46 mm, 0.38 mm and 0.23 mm, respectively. The results of the obtained spectra are shown in Fig. 11 (a) – (d). It can be seen that the profile of the spectra is less disturbed when the spatial resolution is higher. This indicates that the sharply varied longitudinal strain disturbed Bragg spectra, and therefore higher spatial resolution is required for the monitoring of stress/strain concentration region.

6 Conclusions

We investigated the applicability of fiber optic distributed monitoring method using the embedded FBG and the OFDR system for CFRP single-lap bonded joints. The FEA results of strain and stress distributions at the joint interface showed that the birefringence effect due to the transverse stress is hardly influential for the purpose of longitudinal strain estimation in this experiment.

At the joint overlap edge, multiple peaks were observed in the obtained spectrum when the spatial resolution of the OFDR system was set as 0.61 mm. It is demonstrated that obtained spectra were less disturbed when higher spatial resolution was set for the OFDR system. We could conclude that higher spatial resolution was required especially for the stress/strain concentration region.

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Fig. 1 Schematic of the OFDR system. TLS: tunable laser source, C: optical 3 dB coupler, D: photo diode detector, M: reflecton mirror.

Fig. 2 Experimentally obtained spectrogram of a 10 cm FBG.

Fig. 3 Optical fiber embedment by co-curing.

Fig. 4 Bonding by metal molds.

Fig. 5 Schematic of the single-lap joint.

	CFRP	Adhesive
(Ex, Ey, Ez) [GPa]	(9.8, 9.8, 154.6)	3.3
(Gxy, Gyz, Gzx) [GPa]	(2.5, 5.3, 5.3)	
(PRxy, PRyz, PRzx)	(0.45, 0.35, 0.35)	0.39

Table 1. Material properties used in FEA.

Fig. 6 Meshes at a joint edge.

Fig. 7 Boundary conditions of the joint finite model.

Fig. 8 Strain and stress distributions calculated by FEA (200 kgf was applied).

(a) $z = 16.0$ mm

(b) $z = 29.0$ mm

Fig. 9 Shift of Bragg spectra when the single-lap bonded joint is under tensile loads.

Fig. 10 Strain measured by FBG and calculated by FEA.

(a) window width = 400 pm (spatial resolution: 0.61 mm)

(b) window width = 600 pm (spatial resolution: 0.46 mm)

(c) window width = 800 pm (spatial resolution: 0.38 mm)

(d) window width = 1000 pm (spatial resolution: 0.23 mm)

Fig. 11 Bragg spectra at $z = 24.0$ mm when individual spatial resolutions were set for the signal processing of the OFDR system.